

CLINICAL ASSESSMENT OF THE RATE OF SALIVATION, SALIVARY THICKNESS AND ENAMEL REMINERALIZATION IN CHILDREN SUFFERING FROM CHRONIC PYELONEPHRITIS

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Resume. One of the urgent problems of dentistry is the prevention and treatment of dental diseases in children with severe somatic pathology. Currently, chronic pyelonephritis is often among severe somatic diseases that lead to disability. According to the Association of Scientists Studying Hemodialysis and Renal Pathology (2007), chronic pyelonephritis (CP) ranks third as a cause of chronic renal failure, which causes growth and development delay, disability, and a significant reduction in life expectancy in affected children.

Key words. Chronic pyelonephritis, sick child, sputum, phlegm, ERTKB- test.

Children with chronic pyelonephritis need a graduated test tube and a stopwatch to conduct research. Sick children are asked to bend the head down, open the mouth slightly and not to swallow saliva, which is allowed to flow freely into a test tube placed on the lower lip. The start and end time of saliva collection is determined (usually 5-15 minutes). Salivation rate is calculated according to the following formula:

$$C_s = \frac{V}{t}$$

Here: C_s is the rate of salivation; V – volume of secreted saliva (in ml); t – saliva collection time (in minutes). The normal rate of unstimulated salivation is $C_s = 0.31-0.6$ ml/min, hyposalivation is diagnosed at $C_s = 0.03-0.3$ ml/min, and hypersecretion is diagnosed at $C_s = 0.61-2.40$ ml/min.

A 1.0 ml micropipette and a stopwatch are needed to determine viscosity in children with chronic pyelonephritis. Before starting the saliva study, the micropipette is filled with water: - water is drawn up to the 1.0 ml mark in a vertically placed test tube; - the test tube is loosened with a finger and the water is allowed to flow out of the test tube for 5 seconds; - the level of water remaining in the test tube is determined (usually 0.08 ml). Thus, they check how much water comes out of the test tube in 5 seconds (usually 0.92 ml). To determine the viscosity of saliva, the test saliva is drawn into an empty calibrated tube, then the saliva is allowed to flow out of the tube for 5 seconds and the volume of saliva released during this time is measured. The viscosity of saliva is calculated according to the following formula:

$$\frac{V_c}{B_B} = \frac{B_c}{B_B} \quad \text{from this} \quad B_B = \frac{V_B B_B}{V_c}$$

Here: V_v is the volume of water released (ml); V_c – the volume of saliva released (ml); B_s - viscosity of saliva (relative); B_v is the viscosity of water (relative). Salivary viscosity is considered positive when it is 1.0-4.0, and negative when it is 6.0-9.0.

Determination of ERTKB- test in children with chronic pyelonephritis T.L. It was conducted according to the method of Redinova and co-authors. Clinical determination of enamel remineralization speed - ERTKB-test can be used when public measures are taken for the prevention and treatment of dental caries. It is technically simple, and its results are easy to interpret. ERTKB-test method: determination of resistance to caries of teeth is carried out as follows. An acidic buffer mixture with pH 0.3-0.6 and methylene blue 2% is prepared

beforehand. An acidic buffer is a demineralizing mixture. To prepare it, 97 ml of hydrochloric acid and 50 ml of salt-sour potassium are taken, mixed, and distilled water is poured to a volume of 200 ml. To give more viscosity, a part of glycerin is added to one part of the mixture. The high viscosity of such a mixture makes it possible to obtain a drop with a constant size of contact with the tooth and a good standing on its surface. Sour fuchsin is added to the demineralizing liquid for better visual control. In this case, the demineralizing mixture is red. Acid tolerance of enamel (demineralization process) is evaluated by the staining intensity of the damaged part of tooth enamel. The degree of coloring is judged by the typographical scale of the shade of blue. We used a ten-point scale, where the least painted color stick got 10% and the darkest painted got 100%. After a day, the damaged part of the tooth enamel is painted again. At this time, the effect of the demineralizing mixture is not applied. If the damaged part of tooth enamel is stained, then this process is repeated after one day. The loss of staining property in the damaged part is considered as its complete recovery. The damaged part of the tooth enamel regenerates in different people in different periods. That is why the remineralizing properties of saliva determine how long it takes for the damaged part of the enamel to lose its ability to paint.

Thus, Susceptibility of tooth enamel to acid (demineralization, or solubility of enamel) in children with chronic pyelonephritis is calculated in percentages, and remineralization ability of saliva is calculated in days. Caries-resistant people have low sensitivity of tooth enamel to acid (less than 40%) and high remineralizing ability of saliva (from 1 to 3 days), and caries-prone people - high sensitivity of tooth enamel to acid (40% and higher) and low remineralizing ability of saliva (more than 3 days) typical. On the basis of the conducted research, a sequential algorithm of learning methods for children with chronic pyelonephritis was created.

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